

From consultation to inclusive engagement: Advancing participatory modeling for net-zero sustainable development

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ABSTRACT

Traditional modeling approaches for net-zero, sustainable development often prioritize technical and expert-driven inputs, producing outputs that overlook critical institutional and behavioral considerations. Although there has been growing interest in participatory approaches and transdisciplinary research in modeling, most processes currently stop at consultation, missing opportunities for deeper stakeholder integration. This paper introduces a structured framework for embedding inclusivity into participatory modeling for Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs). Drawing on a mixed-methods study, including a systematic literature review, an online stakeholder survey, and semi-structured interviews with modelers and members of a EU-funded project, we identify three interlinked pillars for an inclusive modeling environment: i) stakeholder representation, ii) engagement dynamics, and iii) collective decision-making. We argue that inclusive participatory modeling is not merely a procedural improvement but a strategic necessity for building models - and informing policies - that are credible, resilient, and socially relevant.

1. Introduction

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have established themselves in a pivotal role at the nexus of science and policy, enabling the exploration of various pathways towards net-zero emissions and sustainable development (van Beek et al., 2020; Braunreiter et al., 2021; Weyant, 2017). By integrating diverse disciplines, methodologies, and tools, IAMs have become relevant, influential determinants in policy-making and implementation, which is prominently exemplified by their use in reports of the IPCC (Beck and Mahony, 2018; Beck and Oomen, 2021). Yet, IAMs face increasing scrutiny regarding their utility and capacity to effectively respond to questions of net-zero, sustainable development (Krawczyk and Braun, 2025), and to provide actionable and effective insights for policy makers (Gambhir et al., 2019; Keppo et al., 2021). UN reports indicate persistent failure to meet climate and sustainability targets (UN, 2024; UNEP, 2024; UNFCCC, 2024), suggesting that IAMs' results struggle to support policies that deliver their intended outcomes.

A critical shortcoming of IAMs is the limited inclusion of stakeholders within the modeling process (Doukas et al., 2018; Low and Schäfer, 2020). Current participatory efforts prioritize scientific and expert-driven knowledge (Fazey et al., 2020; Steen et al., 2018), which

leads to outputs that are often too abstract (Peng et al., 2021), overly complex (Braunreiter et al., 2021), or misaligned with institutional and behavioral factors that shape real-world transitions (Doukas and Nikas, 2020). Moreover, it allows vested interests to capture the modeling process (Lim et al., 2023; Royston et al., 2023). IAMs are increasingly subject to 'political calibration' (van Beek et al., 2022) within a *policy-based evidence making* paradigm (Ellenbeck and Lilliestam, 2019, p. 75), limiting alternative transformative pathways (Klenk and Meehan, 2015; Workman et al., 2020).

To address these issues a deeper integration of a diverse range of stakeholders into the modeling process is essential (Braunreiter et al., 2021; Jäger et al., 2023; Royston et al., 2023). This research thus inquires: *How can an inclusive modeling environment be conceptually defined and practically established to better represent diverse stakeholder perspectives, knowledge, and interests?* We draw on a case study from the project "Delivering the next generation of Open Integrated Assessment Models for net-zero, sustainable development" (DIAMOND, for its acronym) – funded by the EU's Horizon Europe Program – which employs a transdisciplinary approach to enhance, expand, and open up six IAMs through open and responsible stakeholder engagement (DIAMOND, 2020).

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While participatory modeling (PM) (Jordan et al., 2018; Voinov et al., 2016) and Transdisciplinary Research (TDR) (McGookin et al., 2024; Nikas et al., 2022) aim to enhance stakeholder engagement in model development, they also face critiques around superficial engagement (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Hedelin et al., 2021; Kok et al., 2021) and inadequate treatment of power dynamics (Dannecker, 2020; Miller and Wyborn, 2020; Zurba et al., 2022). These issues suggest that current participatory approaches not only fall short of their transformative potential but may also reinforce the very dynamics they seek to challenge (Kujala et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2023; Steen et al., 2018; Turnhout et al., 2020). This study responds to the need to rethink how participatory modeling endeavors are designed and implemented.

Recent contributions offer principles and frameworks for guiding meaningful (Bell and Reed, 2021; Norström et al., 2020; Sorgen et al., 2025), equitable (Lieu et al., 2023; Parzonko et al., 2025, Wilson et al., 2025), or pragmatic (McGookin et al., 2024, Milanzi and Schelly, 2025, Punjabi et al., 2025) stakeholder engagement. Yet few studies successfully integrate PM with TDR in the context of climate policy and sustainable development; exceptions such as Jäger et al. (2023) are rare. Our study then uniquely contributes to the scholarly discussion on stakeholder engagement and participation by means of a grounded framework of an inclusive modelling environment.

This paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents the research rationale, followed by section 3 presenting an overview of the materials and steps in the mixed-methods approach we used. Section 4 provides the results of this research, highlighting the key elements, principles and practices that promote inclusive stakeholder engagement. Subsequently, the testing of the designed framework within the DIAMOND project is outlined in section 5, and the elements, principles, and practices from section 4 are enriched by strategies in practice. In section 6, the contributions this work makes to the field of PM and TDR are explored, and this research's implications for environmental policy are presented. The conclusion summarizes the role that inclusivity within PM has for evidence-based policy-making in the context of net-zero, sustainable development.

2. Rationale

This section examines key gaps in current modeling approaches, limitations of existing stakeholder engagement practices, and the potential of TDR as a more holistic framework for stakeholder integration. While this study focuses on IAMs, we deliberately draw on insights from the broader participatory modelling literature, including energy systems and social-ecological modelling, where participatory engagement practices have been extensively explored.

2.1. Balancing power and responsibility in modeling

Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) have grown in influence alongside the climate policy agenda and today are influential, institutionalized determinants in policy-making and implementation (van Beek et al., 2020; McLaren and Markusson, 2020). However, recent scrutiny has spotlighted IAMs' increasing influence and raises concerns, particularly regarding i) limited transparency in IAMs' methods, limitations and assumptions (Gambhir et al., 2019; Krawczyk and Braun, 2025), ii) their treatment as definitive evidence rather than exploratory tools (Braunreiter et al., 2021; Workman et al., 2020), iii) the inherently normative and political nature of model development (Beck and Krueger, 2016; Ellenbeck and Lilliestam, 2019), iv) their 'political calibration' (van Beek et al., 2022) within a *policy-based evidence making* paradigm (Ellenbeck and Lilliestam, 2019, p. 75), v) their multi-national scale that lacks connection to location-specific realities (Krawczyk and Braun, 2025) and contributes to meta-political misrepresentation

(Rubiano Rivadeneira and Carton, 2022), and vi) their imposition of a *view from nowhere* (Rubiano Rivadeneira and Carton, 2022, p.6) that obscures situated knowledge and fails to explicitly address multi-dimensional justice concerns. These trends challenge the integrity of modeling practices: compromising scientific robustness and credibility (Keppo et al., 2021), threatening scientific neutrality (Beck and Mahony, 2018), and creating a false sense of scientific legitimacy (Low and Schäfer, 2020). To reliably inform policy makers on matters of net-zero, sustainable development, it is however imperative that decision support models, such as IAMs, and their results be perceived as credible, relevant and legitimate (Cash et al., 2003; Doukas and Nikas, 2020; Weyant, 2017). As efforts to bolster IAMs' policy relevance increase, so do the risks of these models becoming instruments of political validation (Süsser et al., 2021; van Beek et al., 2022) rather than tools for exploring the transition pathways necessary to deliver a net-zero future that respects planetary and social boundaries (Braunreiter et al., 2021; Krawczyk and Braun, 2025).

2.2. The role of stakeholder engagement

Participatory Modelling seeks to address these issues by emphasizing the engagement of stakeholders in model development (Jordan et al., 2018; Voinov et al., 2016), enhancing the credibility, legitimacy, and robustness of modeling results (Keppo et al., 2021; Kunseler et al., 2015; McGookin et al., 2021), and fostering commitment to the derived results (Gray et al., 2018; Schmidt et al., 2020). However, practical challenges remain (Campfens et al., 2025; Sterling et al., 2019). Certain stakeholder groups tend to be over- or underrepresented (Hedelin et al., 2021), and many are excluded due to the technical nature of modeling (Jordan et al., 2018). Also, differences in power among stakeholders, and conflicts between them often remain unaddressed, undermining PM efforts (Hedelin et al., 2021; Sterling et al., 2019). In the context of net-zero, sustainable development, the inclusion of both scenario users (i.e. policy-makers) (Roelfsema et al., 2022), and those most affected by policy outcomes (Mader and Pohl, 2024; Pisano et al., 2015) is critical. Moving beyond consultation to involve stakeholders in a meaningful way in setting research directions and shaping model outcomes (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; McGookin et al., 2021) ensures that policies are grounded in a realistic understanding of i) societal transformations (McGookin et al., 2024; Nikas et al., 2020), and ii) the desired technological and regulatory innovations (Doukas and Nikas, 2020). Questions around "Who gets to imagine the future?" and "Whose vision counts?" (Beck and Oomen, 2021, p.176) highlight the need for a more inclusive approach to model development, exploring alternatives beyond techno-economic optimization (Beck, 2018; Beck and Oomen, 2021).

2.3. Transdisciplinarity as the next frontier

Transdisciplinary Research has been proposed as a more holistic approach for achieving true integration of diverse stakeholders' perspectives, knowledge, and interests (Mauser et al., 2013; Nikas et al., 2022), providing methods for weaving together different worldviews and navigating potential conflicts (Lang et al., 2012; Norström et al., 2020; Pohl et al., 2021). TDR seeks to i) democratize knowledge production (McGookin et al., 2021), ii) enrich the scientific process with multiple perspectives (Lang et al., 2012), and iii) develop actionable outputs grounded in a broad spectrum of experiences and expectations (Doukas and Nikas, 2020; Nikas et al., 2020). Despite these promises, most collaborative initiatives remain limited to a mere bureaucratic requirement (Lemos et al., 2018) or performative discourse (Nogueira et al., 2021), and stakeholder engagement tends to remain superficial, tokenistic, or centered on expert elicitation (Galende-Sánchez and

Sorman, 2021; Kok et al., 2021). Moreover, the role of power and politics in shaping processes and outcomes tends to remain under-considered (Dannecker, 2020; Miller and Wyborn, 2020; Zurba et al., 2022). These issues reveal that current participatory approaches fall short of their transformative potential, and unintended or negative outcomes prevail (Kujala et al., 2022; Lim et al., 2023; Steen et al., 2018; Turnhout et al., 2020).

To realize their transformative potential, participatory approaches must be reassessed to address how these processes are designed, whose voices are prioritized, and how power is distributed throughout. Drawing from PM and TDR, this study explores how inclusive stakeholder engagement can be operationalized within IAMs to i) embrace the full spectrum of stakeholder insights and ii) challenge entrenched dynamics (Díaz-Reviriego et al., 2019; Meadow et al., 2015; Montfort et al., 2025), thereby better reflecting the complexity, diversity, and political dynamics of real-world sustainability transitions.

3. Materials and methods

The mixed-methods approach (Creswell and Clark, 2017) applied to investigate key elements and principles fostering inclusivity in PM for net-zero, sustainable development combined a systematic literature review (Xiao and Watson, 2019), an online survey (Toepoel, 2016), and semi-structured interviews (Kallio et al., 2016). The insights from this approach were enriched through participant observation (Kawulich, 2005), and a stakeholder elicitation. In an iterative process composed of three steps (Fig. 1), inspired by grounded theory (Priest et al., 2002), we combined qualitative and quantitative methods to develop a framework for inclusive stakeholder engagement. The systematic literature review and participant observation informed an initial conceptual framework, with themes organized via open coding. The survey and interview findings refined the framework, and feedback from modelers and scholars was additionally integrated to enhance real-world applicability. Eventually, all data were synthesized into a cohesive framework outlining elements, principles, and strategies for inclusive stakeholder engagement.

3.1. Case study setting

The Horizon Europe project DIAMOND served as the case study for this research, implementing a strategic framework to enhance the transdisciplinary nature of IAMs. Its consortium of 19 institutions across 19 countries works to make IAMs more inclusive, transparent, and aligned with real-world policy goals through open and responsible stakeholder engagement, pioneering a collaborative knowledge production process (DIAMOND, 2020). In section 5, we describe the strategies employed for implementing the designed framework in practice and analyze the effects this had on the case's stakeholder engagement process.

3.2. Systematic literature review

A systematic literature review (Xiao and Watson, 2019) explored stakeholder engagement practices in modeling and policymaking for sustainability, synthesizing knowledge and developing higher-order constructs.

Data collection. Searches were guided by predefined inclusion and exclusion criteria and a structured keyword strategy (Appendix A). An initial narrow search was conducted in Google Scholar and Semantic Scholar using the term “inclusive stakeholder engagement”, reviewing the first five pages of results. Subsequent searches employed combinations of overarching keywords including: i) participatory modeling, ii) integrated assessment model, iii) representation stakeholder, and iv) policy maker stakeholder. References were complemented by those from the DIAMOND proposal and colleague-recommended papers. Iterative forward and backward citation searches using citation networks ensured comprehensive coverage. The study's staged selection process is summarized according to the PRISMA protocol in Appendix A.1.

Data analysis. Selected literature was analyzed qualitatively with thematic analysis (Lochmiller, 2021), and key themes were extracted using Mendeley. Insights on gaps and challenges in PM informed the initial synthesis process.

Fig. 1. Iterative process for developing the framework of an inclusive modeling environment. The framework was developed through three stages, combining literature review, participant observation, a survey, interviews, and contributor feedback to progressively refine and validate its components. SE = stakeholder engagement. Source: Own elaboration.

3.3. Online survey

An online survey captured stakeholder perceptions of engagement barriers and opportunities, collecting both quantitative and qualitative data for insights into PM practices. Stakeholders were defined as policymakers, representatives of emissions-intensive industries, NGOs, and citizens' energy and climate groups. Twenty-eight questions, including multiple-choice, Likertscale, and open-ended formats, were developed based on the initial conceptual framework (Blair, 2015; Lenzner and Menold, 2016; Toepoel, 2016) (Appendix B). The survey was administered via Unipark for secure data collection and storage.

Data collection. The survey was distributed to 1215 newsletter subscribers of the DIAMOND project and its predecessors, two other research projects in the EU with similar features as DIAMOND, and 568 additional stakeholders identified through a semi-automatic stakeholder elicitation process. We received 101 responses from various sectors: 50.5% of the participants were from NGOs, 27.3% from Academia and Research, and less than 10% from each of the other sectors, with at least one representative per sector (Government and Public Administration, International Organization, Community and Citizens' Association, Business and Industry, Consultancy (categories based on Ernst et al. (2017) and Jäger et al., (2023)). Given the strong representation of policymakers, industry representatives and academics in DIAMOND, the semi-automatic stakeholder elicitation specifically had a focus on networks of NGOs to understand their perception of barriers to and opportunities for stakeholder engagement. Also, most respondents (82.7%) had already previously participated in activities involving collaboration with various partners to promote net-zero, sustainable development, while 8.9% reported no prior invitations.

Data analysis. Quantitative data were analyzed using R, and qualitative responses were coded in MAXQDA (Appendix C).

3.4. Semi-structured interviews

Fourteen semi-structured interviews (Kallio et al., 2016) explored themes of representation, stakeholder differences, and decision-making in the DIAMOND project, as these were the pillars in the initial framework, providing complementary qualitative data on the modelers' perspectives. Guided by six themes (Appendix D) and 25 questions informed by the initial conceptual framework and preliminary survey findings, interviews followed open-ended prompts (Castillo-Montoya, 2016).

Data collection. Conducted via Zoom with modelers, advisory board members, and coordinators of DIAMOND, as well as stakeholder engagement experts from other projects – such as Paris Reinforce, IAM

Compact, and World Trans – interviews lasted 30–60 min. The members of the advisory board were selected based on their experience with and interest in stakeholder engagement, while the modelers were selected based on their role and responsibility in the modeling process. Data was pseudonymized and transcribed with Trint.

Data analysis. Thematic analysis (Lochmiller, 2021), employing abductive coding (Linneberg and Korsgaard, 2019), incorporated interview transcripts, workshop notes, project-internal reports and deliverables, as well as open-text survey responses (Appendix C). The first cycle of coding built on the initial framework, but also remained open to unexpected findings and emerging themes throughout the data. In the second cycle of coding, first-cycle codes were combined into theoretically informed categories and differences within the codes were explored to deepen the analysis and uncover nuanced insights. The interpretive phase then focused on identifying connections and disconnections across the categories to synthesize themes. This phase involved identifying and elaborating new concepts, as well as refining the relationships between these concepts, to refine and complement the initial framework.

4. A cohesive framework for inclusive stakeholder engagement

This section distills the analysis into a three-pillar framework that offers a reflective approach to inclusive stakeholder engagement in participatory modeling. Drawing on the key elements uncovered by the main author during the analytical process, the framework couples a succinct conceptual definition with concrete measures for practical implementation. Each pillar is anchored by three elements, of which one is an overarching task, and an intended outcome; for every element we articulate a guiding principle and illustrate supporting practices. Fig. 2 offers a visual overview, while Table 1 details the principles and practices associated with each pillar.

The three pillars are inherently interdependent and mutually reinforcing. While they may appear sequential (e.g., it makes sense to first identify stakeholders before their knowledge can be integrated), the framework does not prescribe a fixed order. Rather, it encourages a reflective and iterative approach in which all aspects are revisited throughout the modeling process. The time, resources, and effort invested in one pillar often benefit the others: for instance, understanding the background of stakeholders (1.2) supports more attentive facilitation (2.3), while giving space for discussion, negotiation, and revision (3.2) can make engagement more appealing to stakeholders (1.3). The pillars are not isolated, self-contained constructs but rather reference points to guide ongoing, structured reflection and adaptation.

Fig. 2. Cohesive framework of an inclusive modeling environment. The three columns and shades differentiate the three pillars of an inclusive modeling environment. Each pillar has three elements that define it, of which one is an over-arching task (underlined). Source: Own elaboration.

Table 1

Elements, practices and principles of an inclusive modeling environment. This table consolidates principles and practices for ensuring a diverse and representative group of stakeholders, engaging them effectively, and incorporating their input into collective decision-making processes. *Source: Own elaboration.*

Pillar	Element	Principle	Practices
Stakeholder Representation <i>Who is included?</i>	1.1 Stakeholder Identification and Selection	Aim for a diverse and representative group of stakeholders	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Organize Structured Outreach • Employ Detailed Planning • Understand Motivation • Set and Manage Expectations • Consider Available Resources • Reduce Participation Barriers • Raise Attractiveness of Engagement • Address Power Dynamics • Moderate Conflict • Offer Several Interaction Options • Be Approachable and Attentive • Employ Open, Non-rigid Formats • Provide Capacity Building Measures • Have attentive and skillful facilitators • Employ Accessibility and Inclusivity Practices • Keep Stakeholders in the Loop • Generate targeted products for all parties • Provide Opportunity for Deliberation • Foster Shared Understanding • Establish Safe Communication Spaces • Use Transparent Methods • Document All Decisions • Prioritize Clear Communication Channels
	1.2 Participation Drivers	Understand and consider the background of stakeholders	
	1.3 Opportunities for Engagement	Make the engagement appealing and convenient	
Engagement Dynamics <i>How are the stakeholders included?</i>	2.1 Navigation of Differences	Facilitate meaningful engagement in the face of stakeholder differences	
	2.2 Adaptable and Flexible Engagement	Meet the stakeholders where they are and trust their decisions	
	2.3 Equitable Participation	Take care to empower marginalized voices	
Collective Decision-Making <i>How is their knowledge included?</i>	3.1 Integration of Stakeholder Feedback	Have stakeholders continuously contribute in a traceable manner	
	3.2 Deliberation and Understanding	Recognize plurality and give space for discussion, negotiation, and revision	
	3.3 Transparent and Open Procedures	Uphold transparency as a foundational value to build trust and credibility	

4.1. Stakeholder representation

The first pillar, **stakeholder representation**, addresses the question: *Who is included?* (from [Lieu et al. 2023](#)). It is grounded in the idea that identifying and engaging a broad spectrum of stakeholders, including those who are marginalized or traditionally excluded from policy-making, is foundational for inclusive stakeholder engagement. The intended outcome from the actions and ideals elaborated in what follows is to achieve **diverse stakeholder representation**. This goal is also emphasized in the selected literature as an integral component of the transdisciplinary co-design approach ([Selloni, 2017](#)).

4.1.1. Key task: stakeholder identification and selection

Stakeholder Representation hinges on the **identification and selection of stakeholders**, and the guiding principle for this task is: *Aim for a diverse and representative group of stakeholders*. Interviewees highlighted the importance of a diverse group of stakeholders, as exemplified through:

“Being able to generate the diversity that you want to explore, I think requires diversity of the people that are feeding in.” (MU1381)

“Trying to ensure that you have as many perspectives represented within model development or afterwards when you’re trying to interpret the result is crucial.” (MT4404)

And, an overwhelming majority (91.3%) of survey respondents also believe that it is (very) important that diverse participants are represented in decision-making processes related to net-zero, sustainable development. At the same time, almost a third of participants (32.3%) (strongly) disagreed with the statement “Participant representation was satisfactory” when rating their most recent experience collaborating on net-zero, sustainable development - highlighting a dissatisfaction with regards to representation in current practices.

To achieve a diverse and representative group of stakeholders, nine interviewees¹ suggested **structured outreach**; many of them coming from a place of dissatisfaction with how outreach was previously

organized and the results it achieved. Structured outreach can include mapping stakeholders to understand the landscape, conducting a barriers analysis to recognize potential obstacles in engagement, and initiating early awareness-raising about the project. Furthermore, **detailed planning** emerged as an important inclusive engagement practice throughout the analysis. Consider, for example, that survey participants mentioned a “well-organized setting” (P47, P63) as a key contribution to a successful process. Through ensuring clarity in i) engagement goals, ii) role distribution, and iii) responsibilities, detailed planning can streamline the process and enhance participation.

4.1.2. Element A: participation drivers

Once identified and selected, it is **participation drivers** that shape a stakeholder’s decision to accept or decline the invitation to contribute. The guiding principle for this element is: *Understand and consider the background of stakeholders*. It is grounded in issues revealed through the interviews about who eventually showed up for engagement activities in previous settings, as exemplified through the following two quotes from the interviews:

“We try to invite like a wide variety of actors. But at the end, [...] only researchers, people from Thinktanks, and commission staff came into the workshop.” (EB4877)

“The majority of the stakeholders involved in the series of workshop were only academia and the government officials.” (ME5787)

In line with the selected literature ([Ernst et al., 2017](#); [Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022](#)) and findings from the participant observation, the survey revealed a broad range of i) participants’ motivation to potentially contribute to DIAMOND, ranging from being driven by a desire to contribute (57.8%), to being affected by the policy outcome (33.8%), as well as ii) their desired achievement, ranging from gaining knowledge or insights (74.4%), to building social networks and connections (57.8%).²

The selected literature underscores the importance of

¹ EB4877, EI1838, EI7171, SN1756, SU3624, ME5787, MS2146, MT4404, and MU1381

² The percentages for this question and following questions do not add up to 100% because respondents were allowed to select multiple answers. Each percentage represents the proportion of respondents who chose that specific option out of the total number of respondents.

understanding stakeholder motivations (Kujala et al., 2022; Sterling et al., 2019). This can happen through tailoring communication to different audiences, and outlining potential take-aways such as learning opportunities and networking. Following insights from the selected literature, **setting and managing expectations** is crucial for fostering more inclusive stakeholder engagement (Ernst et al., 2017; Sterling et al., 2019). This was echoed in the interviews, for example:

“It’s a matter of just setting the expectations right in the beginning.” (MU1381)

Expectation management comes down to defining a clear and communicable outcome, and ensuring stakeholders understand both i) why they participate, and ii) what is expected of them. Such clarity supports stakeholders in comprehending both the benefits they may gain and the commitments involved. Further, as highlighted in the selected literature, **considering the available resources** of stakeholders is essential to overcoming barriers to sustained engagement, particularly among marginalized groups (Kok et al., 2021; Turnhout et al., 2020). Practical measures such as financial reimbursements, and material stakeholders can use to garner support for their engagement, can significantly enhance their ability to participate.

4.1.3. Element B: opportunities for engagement

For stakeholder representation it is also necessary to consider what we refer to as the **opportunities for engagement**. The guiding principle for this element is: *Make the engagement appealing and convenient*. This can be considered as a response to the reports by interviewees on how difficult it is i) to make stakeholders interested in the topic of IAMs, and ii) to keep them engaged, as exemplified through the following two quotes:

“Regular people don’t like models. They don’t trust models.” (SN1756)

“[Stakeholders] are going to say like, ‘What is this? I don’t even understand the title of this work, so why am I even gonna go’.” (EB4877)

This element was also informed by the selected literature, particularly by Jäger et al. (2023), who focused on designing engagement processes that stakeholders would find compelling and easy to participate in.³

Addressing barriers to participation, such as time constraints, is highlighted as crucial for inclusive stakeholder engagement in the selected literature (Ernst et al., 2017; Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Hedelin et al., 2021). The results from the online survey reinforce this notion, as almost two-third (62.2%) of participants selected “lack of time” as what has hindered them to come to engagement activities in the past. Some barriers to participation can be addressed by i) allowing flexible registration options, and ii) providing online engagement opportunities to cater to stakeholders unable to attend in person. Additionally, **increasing the appeal of engagement activities** is identified in the selected literature as a way to boost stakeholder interest and attendance (Jäger et al., 2023). This can include inviting prominent speakers and scheduling sessions around major events such as the COP.

4.2. Engagement dynamics

The second pillar, **engagement dynamics**, focuses on the question: *How are the stakeholders included?* This pillar outlines components for maintaining active and meaningful stakeholder participation, ensuring that all voices are heard and respected throughout the modeling process. The intended outcome from the actions and ideals elaborated in what follows is to achieve **stakeholder empowerment**. This is also identified

in the selected literature as an integral objective of stakeholder engagement itself (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Jordan et al., 2018).

4.2.1. Key task: navigation of differences

Given the diverse group of stakeholders identified through the first pillar, differences among them are inevitable - differences, which need to be navigated in both PM (Voinov et al., 2018) and TDR (Lang et al., 2012) contexts. The guiding principle for this task is therefore: *Facilitate meaningful engagement in the face of stakeholder differences*. Interviewees emphasized that “the very goal of the process [is] to understand the difference with the stakeholders” (WN4312).

In line with the selected literature (Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022; Sterling et al., 2019; Turnhout et al., 2020), interviewees identified **addressing power dynamics** as crucial to creating an inclusive modeling environment:

“We all know that these power differences exist. But for a few hours in our workshop, at least, let’s forget about them.” (EI1838)

This resonates with the finding that “differences in power between various stakeholders” have been highlighted as a key barrier to establishing a common ground during engagement activities, reflecting a quarter (25.0%) of the open-text responses to the respective survey item (Item 5.1). Suggested practices for addressing power dynamics include organizing separate preliminary meetings for different - and particularly marginalized - groups, and maintaining balanced participation during discussions. Additionally, **moderating conflict** is essential to move towards inclusivity, considering that more than a third (36.1%) of participants selected “discomfort with conflict” as what has hindered them or others to speak up and contribute in engagement activities. Some ways to do that are setting clear guidelines for interaction, agreeing on prioritized values, and employing mediated negotiations when necessary.

4.2.2. Element A: adaptable and flexible engagement

To accommodate the needs of diverse participants, **adaptable and flexible engagement** is crucial, which is demonstrated by the omnipresence of these keywords in various interview- and survey-responses. The guiding principle for this element is: *Meet the stakeholders where they are and trust their decisions*; which is rooted in the following statement:

“I find it’s worth time listening to the participants [...]. If the right group is engaged, then trust them on the value of the initiative.” (P17)

In practice, adaptable and flexible engagement can be implemented through **offering multiple interaction options**. This has been suggested by several interviewees:

“You should have both option available: you can in the background, you can write it down, or you can speak it. So you can do both.” (EI7171)

“Rather than just say, look, we’re going to have a stakeholder meeting and there’s 15, 20 people here on the line, [...] offer like if anybody would like to talk to us, you know, one on one.” (SO8546)

These options can thus look like switching between group activities and one-on-one meetings or providing online platforms for ongoing commentary, which enables stakeholders to engage in ways that best suit their preferences and abilities. To **enhance approachability and attentiveness**, two concepts introduced in the selected literature (Ernst et al., 2017; Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022), all of a project’s consortium members are encouraged to demonstrate active listening, and show genuine interest in stakeholders’ contributions. This emphasis is echoed beyond the literature, aligning with a best practice recommendation from the survey:

³ The project Exploring National and Global Actions to reduce Greenhouse gas Emissions (ENGAGE) (<https://engage-climate.org/>) described in Jäger et al. (2023) stands out as one of the first successful applications of TDR for effectively integrating IAMs and PM in the context of climate policy and sustainable development.

“To enhance inclusivity: [...] pay attention, actively listen, and really show that you care for what the participant is saying.” (P66)

Additionally, the selected literature highlights the value of **open, non-rigid formats** (Sterling et al., 2019). This can involve splitting stakeholders into smaller groups, as well as allowing them to make meaningful decisions about the engagement design themselves.

4.2.3. Element B: equitable participation

According to the selected literature, **equitable participation** is central to engaging diverse stakeholders. (Norström et al., 2020). The guiding principle for this element is: *Take care to empower marginalized voices.*; drawn from the following open-text response from the survey:

“Building everyone’s knowledge at the same pace, encouraging participants to question and challenge experts - basically *empowering* [emphasis added] the seldom heard voices to contribute in a meaningful way for themselves as well as the process.” (P46)

Providing capacity-building measures was identified by five interviewees⁴ as a meaningful practice to empower stakeholders, which matches insights from the participant observation and internal documentation (Briers and Vienni-Baptista, 2024). Capacity building can entail i) training for effective participation, and ii) providing background materials on discussion topics, which equips less experienced stakeholders with the necessary tools and knowledge to contribute confidently. In addition, both survey participants and interviewees emphasized the importance of **attentive and skillful facilitators**. Consider the following successful experiences as described by survey participants, for example:

“Open ideation [...] guided by an excellent professional enhances time efficiency and maintains the feeling of ‘no bad ideas’ among the participants.” (P97)

“Having awareness persons and feminist moderation trying to think about pronouns of people, about language barriers, and about the different knowledge backgrounds people have.” (P76)

Meanwhile, one interviewee warned that, without facilitation, “those who don’t like conflict will just shut up” (SN1756). The facilitator’s responsibilities include guiding discussions thoughtfully, asking relevant questions, and sharing experiences. Lastly, **accessibility and inclusivity practices** unsurprisingly emerged from the coding process, with ten interviewees⁵ mentioning practices that could be categorized in this group, given that “within [Project name anonymized for review], [the consortium] wants a much more inclusive approach” (MT4404). In practice, this can look like using simple language, designing awareness programs, and fostering an inclusive team culture.

4.3. Collective decision-making

The third pillar, **collective decision-making**, answers the question: *How is their knowledge included?* and emphasizes the continuous integration of stakeholder feedback into the modeling process. These practices are essential for ensuring that the final outputs of the modeling process are genuinely informed by stakeholder contributions. The intended outcome from the actions and ideals elaborated in what follows is, therefore, to achieve **stakeholder ownership**. This is also identified in the selected literature as a core objective of stakeholder engagement in itself (Hedelin et al., 2021).

4.3.1. Key task: integration of stakeholder feedback

In the context of inclusive stakeholder engagement, the **integration of stakeholder feedback** ensures that stakeholder contributions are not only solicited but also meaningfully incorporated into the decision-making process, thereby making it a collective one. The respective

principle is: *Have stakeholder continuously contribute in a traceable manner*. Continuity was mentioned as relevant for an inclusive modeling environment in the interviews, as exemplified through:

“Ensuring that, as far as possible, all perspectives are included *throughout the process* [emphasis added] - model development, interpreting results, developing scenarios, and so on.” (MT4404)

Meanwhile, traceability was identified as a gap in current PM practices in the selected literature (Sterling et al., 2019).

The practice of **keeping stakeholders in the loop**, as described by interviewee EI1838, ensures continuous engagement and appreciation of their input, for example through i) follow-ups after engagement activities, and ii) regular and timely updates on progress. The survey results also emphasize the importance of an ongoing dialogue, as exemplified through “timely and meaningful communication of progress and updates” being selected by two-thirds (66.2%) of survey participants as contributing to a successful process. Furthermore, the selected literature highlights the importance of **targeted outcomes tailored to different stakeholder groups** as a means of (re)integrating and applying co-produced knowledge in TDR (Lang et al., 2012). Such practices not only help stakeholders recognize the tangible impacts of their contributions, but also strengthen their commitment to the project.

4.3.2. Element A: deliberation and understanding

Deliberation and understanding captures the conditions necessary for the meaningful elicitation of stakeholders’ perspectives, knowledge, and priorities. The guiding principle for this element is: *Recognize plurality and give space for discussion, negotiation, and revision*. It builds on Norström et al. (2020)’s “pluralistic” principle for knowledge co-production, and is supported by the following insight from a survey participant:

“Proactive measures are needed [...] that impede a truly democratic and transformative deliberative process. This includes [...] recognizing *plurality* [emphasis added].” (P117)

Several strands of practices tie into enabling and fostering discussion, negotiation, and revision. One key strand involves **providing opportunities for deliberation**, i.e. providing platforms where stakeholders can present and engage with diverse perspectives. The selected literature identifies this as a critical response to existing gaps in current participatory practices (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Sterling et al., 2019). In practice, this can look like embracing questions, feedback, and critique, as well as allowing communication forms that do not center around consensus, and planning enough time and opportunities for expression of views and discussion. **Fostering shared understanding**, i.e. stakeholders’ understanding of each other’s positions and the project at hand, has been identified in the selected literature as central to facilitating dialogue and collective decision-making (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022; Sterling et al., 2019). Notably, shared understanding does not imply consensus or the elimination of differing perspectives and worldviews, either during or as a result of the decision-making process (Conklin, 2005; Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022), rather it is a condition where “stakeholders understand each other’s positions well enough to have intelligent dialogue about the different interpretations of the problem” (Conklin, 2005). Practices that support this include clearly stating what the results will be and how they will be used, facilitating the examination of assumptions and values of models, and making everyone talk. Furthermore, **establishing safe communication spaces**, which ensure that stakeholders feel comfortable, safe and secure sharing their perspective, insights and concerns, is highlighted in the selected literature as a key element of inclusive stakeholder engagement practice (Ernst et al., 2017; Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022; Sterling et al., 2019). Through planning breaks

⁴ MT4404, MB7437, SO8546, EI1711, and WN4312

⁵ WN4312, EB4877, EI1838, EI1711, SO8546, MB7437, ME5787, MP6044, MS2146, and MU1381

Table 2
Strategies employed for implementing an inclusive modelling environment in practice.

Pillar	Element	Strategies in Practice
Stakeholder Representation <i>Who is included?</i>	1.1 Stakeholder Identification and Selection	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Decentralized, personalized outreach process • List of invitees enriched through database of underrepresented stakeholders
	1.2 Participation Drivers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear communication to stakeholders about why they participate and what they can expect • Thematically focused sessions
	1.3 Opportunities for Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engagement offered online • Stakeholders choose workshop date and time • Prominent keynote speakers
Engagement Dynamics <i>How are the stakeholders included?</i>	2.1 Navigation of Differences	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Review workshop dynamics in the break to act • Monitor and pursue who and what needs more focus
	2.2 Adaptable and Flexible Engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Workshops specifically not (just) about modeling • Demonstrated interest in the stakeholders and what they are contributing, acknowledging and appreciating what they were saying • Open discussion group format, online survey tool, and option to review workshop material post-workshop
	2.3 Equitable Participation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stakeholders' profiles reviewed beforehand and utilized in the workshop to ask them relevant questions • Workshop's material shared beforehand • Built capacity of consortium members to skillfully facilitate
Collective Decision-Making <i>How is their knowledge included?</i>	3.1 Integration of Stakeholder Feedback	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Follow up after workshops through sharing a report • Documentation of integration demonstrating how feedback was integrated
	3.2 Deliberation and Understanding	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questions, feedback, and critique embraced • Time and opportunities planned for expression of views and discussion • Stakeholders split into smaller, more homogeneous groups (based on thematic focus) that feel less threatening
	3.3 Transparent and Open Procedures	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Voting of stakeholder priorities and modeling feasibility established to document what decisions were made and for what reason

for informal exchange, splitting up stakeholders in groups that feel less threatening, and having stakeholders exchange among each other before opening the plenum discussion spaces can be made more safe to communicate in. All three strands of practices resonate well with survey data, for example, where participants described a successful participatory process they've been involved in:

"Thanks to the focus on dialogue, it was possible to create a regenerative atmosphere despite different opinions." (P117)

"Safe and friendly space for expressing ourselves with reduced power asymmetries and dynamics; openness to dialogue and constructive critics." (P24)

"It was exciting and productive since all participants had a clear objective, the time to discuss was equal to research understanding, and no barriers of language or knowledge were limiting the outcome." (P97)

4.3.3. Element B: transparent and open procedures

Transparent and open processes are identified in the selected literature as foundational to building trust and credibility in stakeholder engagement (Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022; Pisano et al., 2015; Voinov et al., 2016), which is why the respective principle is *Uphold transparency as a foundational value to build trust and credibility*. Transparency has also been highlighted as a key contributor to inclusivity in the interviews, as exemplified through:

"Inclusivity goes with being more open [...] and also being more transparent." (EB4877).

Employing transparent methods reflects a vision interviewees expressed with regards to more inclusive stakeholder engagement. It can look like using simple, understandable models, complemented with clear textual explanations and visualizations. Furthermore, three interviewees⁶ highlight **documenting all decisions** as a strategy to enhance inclusivity, driven by the rationale that thorough documentation contributes to both accountability and transparency. Meanwhile, **prioritizing clear communication channels** emerged from the fact that they were emphasized as pivotal for an accessible, appealing, or convenient participatory experience by participants of the online survey, being the most prominent response (57.8%) for the respective item

(Item 6.5). This practice includes ensuring that as much material as possible is open access to support an environment where information is freely available and consistently delivered.

5. Application of the framework within DIAMOND

The designed framework was then tested in the context of the DIAMOND project, for which it proved helpful for reflecting on the stakeholder engagement process and promoting inclusivity. Table 2 outlines the strategies employed to implement the framework when co-creating novel scenario spaces. This process involved a webinar, and two workshops each on the topics of *climate change*, *climate action*, and *user-driven scenarios* (Briers and Vienni-Baptista, 2025). Our framework influenced the selection of stakeholders, the constellation of how they were put together in the workshops, and our understanding of the stakeholders' role. The framework contributed to selecting a diverse group of stakeholders, together with a low dropout rate, and meaningful, critical contributions from all participants. It also facilitated a transparent, traceable deliberation process. As such, the DIAMOND experience demonstrates the framework's value as a practical tool for enhancing inclusivity in real-world participatory modeling settings, drawing attention to the often-overlooked procedural, relational, and reflexive conditions that proved critical for fostering meaningful participation throughout the process.

6. Discussion

Integrated Assessment Models struggle with producing knowledge that aligns with the practical, institutional, and socio-political demands of net-zero, sustainable development (Doukas and Nikas, 2020; Doukas et al., 2018). The persistent disconnect between international policy goals and realized actions (UN, 2024; UNEP, 2024; UNFCCC, 2024) underscores the limitations of traditional, technocratic modeling paradigms (Beck and Oomen, 2021; Fazey et al., 2020; Sterling et al., 2019). Addressing these gaps requires participatory approaches that embed diverse knowledge systems (Lieu et al., 2023), attend to power dynamics (Turnhout et al., 2020), and support genuine deliberation and co-production of knowledge (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Sterling et al., 2019). This study responds by introducing a novel

⁶ WN4312, MP6044, and SN1756

cohesive framework for inclusivity in the context of PM. By reimagining stakeholder engagement as a continuous, adaptive, and power-sensitive process, the framework aims to improve the social robustness, relevance, and legitimacy of IAMs. In what follows, we elaborate on the framework's implications for i) participatory modeling and Transdisciplinary Research, and ii) environmental policy and governance.

6.1. Implications for participatory modeling and transdisciplinary research

While PM and TDR both emphasize stakeholder engagement, critiques highlight persistent implementation gaps, as discussed in section 2. This framework responds to these critiques by offering a structured, actionable approach to inclusivity, grounded in the academic literature and empirical insights from the DIAMOND project. Within DIAMOND, the framework guided reflection and decision-making across multiple stages of the stakeholder engagement process and contributed to obtaining outcomes such as a low dropout rate, high-quality stakeholder input, and the ability to trace how feedback informed modeling assumptions. These empirical insights offer preliminary evidence of the framework's practical value and may be extended in future applications of the framework. The framework draws attention to the often-overlooked procedural, relational, and reflexive conditions that shape stakeholder engagement in modeling. It articulates three interlinked pillars: i) stakeholder representation, ii) engagement dynamics, and iii) collective decision-making.

Stakeholder representation responds to the central question of "Who is included?" by advancing practices toward meaningful diversity. While representativeness has become an established concern in PM settings (Voinov et al., 2016), diversity remains underexplored and inconsistently applied (Sterling et al., 2019; Lieu et al., 2023). This framework addresses these gaps by incorporating an awareness of diverse motivations, expectations, and participation barriers - elements surfaced in both literature (Ernst et al., 2017; Sterling et al., 2019) and empirical findings - and by proposing concrete outreach and engagement strategies to address them. In doing so, it aligns with recognition-based critiques of participation (Fraser, 2009; Lieu et al., 2023), contributing to both the legitimacy and the comprehensiveness of modeling processes (Cash et al., 2003; Keppo et al., 2021).

Engagement dynamics shift focus from *who* participates to *how* they participate. Recognizing that presence alone is insufficient, the framework embeds principles for active moderation, conflict navigation, and power-sensitive facilitation - key for addressing the asymmetries that undermine equitable engagement (Ernst et al., 2017; Kenny and Castilla-Rho, 2022; Turnhout et al., 2020) - as well as measures to address IAMs' inaccessibility due to their complexity (Keppo et al., 2021). Literature and empirical data affirm the need for i) flexible, attentive, and adaptive formats (Ernst et al., 2017; Jäger et al., 2023; Selloni, 2017) ii) and approaches that makes it easy for stakeholders to understand and engage with the models (Braunreiter et al., 2021). Our findings support these aspects as central to enabling interaction that is inclusive and meaningful. In operationalizing these elements, the framework reinforces TDR's inclusive ideals and strengthens PM's ability to reflect complex and contested social realities.

Collective decision-making confronts the critique that participatory processes often amount to symbolic consultation. Instead, it establishes practices for the continuous, traceable integration of stakeholder feedback - key tenets of co-production and procedural integrity (Pohl et al., 2021; McGookin et al., 2021; Voinov et al., 2016). Acknowledging that these ideals are unevenly implemented in practice (Galende-Sánchez and Sorman, 2021; Sterling et al., 2019), the

framework emphasizes transparent documentation and iterative engagement, embedding participation across the full modeling lifecycle. This makes stakeholder contributions both visible and impactful, reinforcing the value of participatory modeling as a vehicle for democratic knowledge co-production.

Together, these pillars operationalize the three core rationales for stakeholder engagement: i) instrumentally, the framework fosters legitimacy, ownership, and accountability (Schoonover et al., 2019; Schmidt et al., 2020), ii) substantively, it improves model quality and contextual relevance through the integration of diverse knowledge systems (Lang et al., 2012; Jäger et al., 2023), and iii) normatively, it affirms the democratic right of those affected by decisions to shape them (Kok et al., 2021; Pisano et al., 2015). In contrast to "legalistic" forms of engagement driven by procedural compliance (Wesselink et al., 2011), this framework fosters a deep integration of a diverse range of stakeholders. By i) making the normative and political dimensions of modeling explicit, and ii) approaching models not as neutral tools, but as discursive spaces for deliberation and negotiation, it brings PM and TDR closer to their transformative potential.

6.2. Implications for environmental policy

By embedding inclusivity into the fabric of PM, the framework strengthens the democratic legitimacy, quality, and equity of modeling processes and resulting policies (Blackstock et al., 2007). In the context of net-zero, sustainable development, where policy success hinges on both credibility and public acceptance (Mader and Pohl, 2024; Pisano et al., 2015; Roelfsema et al., 2022), these qualities are essential. The framework's implications for environmental policy can be grouped into three key areas: i) enhancing democratic legitimacy, ii) improving policy relevance and actionability, and iii) promoting equity in environmental governance. Together, these dimensions highlight how inclusive modeling practices can address current gaps in participatory processes while fostering more robust, equitable, and impactful policies. Each of these areas is discussed in detail below.

6.2.1. Enhancing democratic legitimacy

Environmental governance often suffers from a democratic deficit, where unequal stakeholder representation exacerbates power imbalances (Hedelin et al., 2021), undermining the legitimacy of both model outcomes and policies (Behagel and Turnhout, 2011; Cvitanovic et al., 2019). This framework addresses these challenges by promoting diverse stakeholder representation (Pillar 1) (Lieu et al., 2023; McGookin et al., 2024) and prioritizing the empowerment of underrepresented voices (Turnhout et al., 2020; Wilson et al., 2025). By involving a broader spectrum of stakeholders, the framework mitigates the risks of "captured" decision-making, where dominant interests prevail (Lim et al., 2023; Royston et al., 2023). Open, transparent, and participatory processes democratize knowledge production (McGookin et al., 2021), increasing societal support and the legitimacy of decision-making processes, as our findings showed.

6.2.2. Improving policy relevance and actionability

Inclusive stakeholder engagement significantly enhances the relevance (Klenk and Meehan, 2015; Workman et al., 2020) and actionability (McGookin et al., 2022) of policies derived from modeling outcomes (Jordan et al., 2018). Participatory methods ensure that models reflect real-world concerns, fostering stakeholder buy-in (Abram et al., 2020) which is critical for implementation (Doukas and Nikas, 2020; McGookin et al., 2021). Without equitable representation, policies risk being perceived as illegitimate (Cash et al., 2003), undermining

their effectiveness and societal acceptance (Blackstock et al., 2007; Braunreiter et al., 2021). By integrating diverse perspectives, the framework ensures that models i) address the complexities of social, economic, and environmental challenges (Delafield et al., 2021; McGookin et al., 2024), and ii) satisfy stakeholders, as our findings showed.

6.2.3. Promoting equity in environmental governance

Equity is a cornerstone of effective environmental governance but is often overlooked in traditional policy-making, leading to outcomes that exacerbate vulnerabilities rather than mitigate them (Stirling, 2006; Ravikumar et al., 2022; Turnhout et al., 2020). This framework prioritizes equitable participation by actively addressing power dynamics and ensuring that diverse perspectives inform decision-making (Basta et al., 2021; Kok et al., 2021). Policy recommendations shaped through such engagement are more equitable (Campfens et al., 2025), and better reflect the needs of all sectors of society not just those with greater political and economic influence (Akaateba et al., 2018; Chu et al., 2016; Nikas et al., 2022).

By redefining the relationship between scientific knowledge production and society, the framework contributes to a more democratic and collaborative approach to environmental governance. This aligns with calls for a new social contract between science and society, where decisions are informed by both scientific knowledge and the lived experiences of communities through genuine collaboration across diverse groups (Fazey et al., 2020).

7. Conclusion

This research presented a framework for inclusive participatory modeling, structured around three interlinked pillars: stakeholder representation, engagement dynamics, and collective decision-making. Each pillar encapsulates actionable principles and practices grounded in PM and TDR through which IAMs and other decision-support tools can evolve to meet the demands of a diverse and rapidly changing world. Inclusivity in PM is not merely a procedural enhancement but a strategic response to the limitations of conventional approaches. By moving beyond consultation toward genuine, ongoing engagement, this framework supports modeling practices that integrate multiple perspectives, interests, and forms of knowledge, thereby reflecting the social, political, and institutional realities of sustainability transitions. In doing so, it improves both the credibility and applicability of model-based insights, laying the groundwork for resilient and socially relevant policy pathways. Future research will focus on applying this framework across additional case contexts and exploring its integration throughout diverse stages of model development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Victoria Herbig: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Stephanie Briers:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Supervision. **Bianca Vienni-Baptista:**

Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of Generative AI and AI-assisted technologies in the writing process

During the preparation of this work the authors used ChatGPT 4o in order to improve the readability of Sections 2 and 6, receiving suggestions for improving the conciseness and clarity of the presentation of thoughts and arguments. After using this tool, the authors reviewed and edited the content as needed and take full responsibility for the content of the published article.

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Declaration of Competing Interest

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Appendix A. literature review protocol

Figure A.1. PRISMA 2020 flow diagram

Table A.2

Keywords used as inclusion criteria in the selection procedure of the literature review

Overarching Keyword	Related Keywords
Inclusivity	accessibility, accessible, diversity, inclusion, inclusive, justice, welcoming
Stakeholder	development, iam, integrated assessment model(s), model(s), modeling, participant(s), participation, participatory, plan(ning)
Engagement	
Sustainability	adaptation, climate action, climate change, decarbonization, environmental, mitigation, net-zero, sustainable
Transdisciplinary	collaborative, co-design, co-production, collective, interdisciplinary, transformative
Representation	civil society, disadvantaged, exclusion, incorporated, incorporation, intersectional, intersectionality, involvement, involved, key, marginalized, marginalization, powerful
Decision Making	argument(s), communication, consensus, conflict(s), contribution(s), critical, dialogue, discussion, dissent, dynamics, empowerment, hierarchy, influence, interaction, negotiation, ownership, power, process, reflective, reflection, reconcile, resolution, revision, truth
Differences	action, agenda, asymmetry, beliefs, bias(es), cultural, culture, emotion(s), expertise, experience, goal, interest(s), knowledge, norm(s), perspective(s), priority, priorities, skill(s), subjectivity, value(s)
Strategies	analysis, atmosphere, balance, balancing, concept(s), condition(s), dimension(s), enabler(s), environment, evaluation, feedback, framework, guide, guidance, innovation, learning(s), lesson(s), method(s), principle(s), progress, room, space, strategy, strategies, tool(s), trade-off(s)
Barriers	challenge(s), difficult(ies), failure(s), gap(s), limitation(s), mistake(s), question(s)
Benefits	expectation(s), impact(s), motivation, success
Policy	actionable, governance, law, policy maker, practical, public, relevant, scenario(s)
Trust	acceptable, accepted, confidence, credibility, fair, free, freedom, genuine, mutual, open, respect, safe, safety, secure, simple, tractable, transparency, transparent

Eligibility criteria:

- Focus on participatory modeling, stakeholder engagement, or integrated assessment modeling
- Situated within public policy, governance, or science-policy-practice interfaces
- Addresses inclusivity, representation, or decision-making

Exclusion criteria:

- Corporate or purely private-sector contexts
- Studies addressing inclusivity only in outcomes (e.g., inclusive governance) without relevance to modeling or engagement processes

Appendix B. Extract from the survey questionnaire

Item 4.1 – Importance of diversity

How important do you think it is for diverse participants to be represented in decision-making processes related to net-zero, sustainable development?

- Not Important
- Somewhat Important
- Important
- Very Important
- I don't know

Item 5.1 – Barriers to shared understanding

In your experience, what hinders initially establishing a common ground during engagement activities? Please select any barriers you perceive.

- Assumptions and underlying principles of models are difficult to understand
- Unclear what outcomes will be and how they will be used
- Unclear what decisions are being made during the process and what their impact is
- Unclear priorities
- Differences between the various participants: *please specify*
- Other: *please specify*

Item 6.5 - accessibility and convenience

What contributes to an enabling environment for participatory processes? Please select all conditions that make engagement activities more accessible, appealing, or convenient.

- Timing close to relevant events (e.g. COP)
- Prominent speakers
- Possibility to register for the session rather than for the event as a whole
- Assistance in learning how to participate effectively
- Breakout groups in different languages
- Reimbursement for participation
- Agreement on values of priority
- Clear communication channels
- Guidelines for interaction
- No need for consensus
- Balanced representation of participants with diverse characteristics
- Other: *please specify*

Appendix C. Codebook extract

Engagement Mechanisms and Tools - Selected Themes

- Rules
- Interactive tools and simulation
 - Gamification
 - Simulator
 - Direct interaction – Dynamic oversight
- Data collection and feedback
 - Writing down
 - Forum with limited visibility to other participants
 - Simple form
 - Surveys
 - Realtime document to note & share thoughts

Inclusive Engagement Practices - Selected Themes

- Interactive and participatory techniques

- o Fostering interactivity
 - Give opportunities
 - Allow everybody to contribute
 - Think-pair-share
 - Make everyone talk
- o Open communication
- Setting and managing expectations
- o Set expectations right
- o Have a concrete outcome
- o Let stakeholders know why they participate
- o Have stakeholders express their objectives
- Operational and transparent processes
- o Robust and transparent processes
 - Robust processes
 - Open and transparent communication channels
 - Use transparent modeling methodologies
- o Feedback and adaptation
 - Allow feedback
 - Keep stakeholders in the loop
 - Follow up

Navigating Differing Viewpoints - Selected Themes

- What brings stakeholders together
- Strategies to negotiate / find compromise
- o Proper logical reasoning
- o Introduce evidence
- o Make everyone talk
- o Understand that interests can contradict and also align
- o Taking time to explain point of view
- Consensus
- Responsibility of facilitator

Appendix D. Semi-structured interview guide: Themes

Theme	Overarching Question(s)	Description
Introduction	1) What is your primary affiliation within [Project name anonymized for review]? 2) What was your role in a successful SE experience?	Brief introduction of the project and interviewer. Basic background info to ease the participant into the conversation.
T1: Expectations	What are your Expectations of [Project name anonymized for review]’s Participatory and Transdisciplinary Approach?	Explores the purpose, motivations, and anticipated outcomes from engagement. Includes preferred engagement levels and timing across the project.
T2: Representation	What are your Thoughts and Perspectives on Representation?	Examines stakeholder selection, the idea of representativeness, and factors influencing participation acceptance.
T3: Stakeholder Differences	What are your Thoughts and Perspectives on Stakeholder Differences?	Focuses on diversity among stakeholders, its impact on power dynamics and potential conflict, and strategies to address these.
T4: Collective Decision-Making	What are your Thoughts and Perspectives on collective Decision-Making?	Covers how to foster shared understanding, reconcile viewpoints, and create safe communication spaces.
T5: Constraints	Integrated throughout follow-up questions.	Identifies barriers to stakeholder engagement and challenges faced by facilitators in creating supportive environments.
T6: Vision	What is your Vision regarding [Project name anonymized for review]’s Participatory and Trans-disciplinary Approach?	Explores enabling environments for inclusive participation, including best-practice strategies and values.
Closing	Would you like to share anything else?	Allow interviewee to add to what they have shared so far.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Abram, S., Aitkins, E., Dietzel, A., Hammond, M., Jenkins, K., Kiamba, L., Kirshner, J., Kreienkamp, J., Pegram, T., Vining, B., 2020. Just Transition: Pathways to Socially Inclusive Decarbonisation. COP26 Universities Network Briefing.
- Akaateba, M.A., Huang, H., Adumpon, E.A., 2018. Between co-production and institutional hybridity in land delivery: Insights from local planning practice in peri-urban tamale, Ghana. *Land Use Policy* 72, 215–226. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2017.12.043>.
- Basta, C., Kunseler, E., Wamsler, C., van der Jagt, A., Baro, F., Balenciaga, I., Bach, M., Wickenberg, B., 2021. Inclusiveness, equity, consistency, and flexibility as guiding criteria for enabling transdisciplinary collaboration: lessons from a European project on nature-based solutions and urban innovation. *Front. Clim.* 3. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fclim.2021.630075>.
- Beck, M., 2018. Telling stories with models and making policy with stories: an exploration. *Clim. Policy* 18, 928–941. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2017.1404439>.
- Beck, M., Krueger, T., 2016. The epistemic, ethical, and political dimensions of uncertainty in integrated assessment modeling. *Wiley Interdisciplinary Reviews: Climate Change* 7 (5), 627–645. [doi:10.1002/wcc.415](https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.415).
- Beck, S., Mahony, M., 2018. The IPCC and the new map of science and politics. *WIREs Clim. Change*. <https://doi.org/10.1002/wcc.547>.
- Beck, S., Oomen, J., 2021. Imagining the corridor of climate mitigation what is at stake in IPCC's politics of anticipation? *Environ. Sci. Policy* 123, 169–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.05.011>.
- Behagel, J., Turnhout, E., 2011. Democratic legitimacy in the implementation of the water framework directive in the Netherlands: towards participatory and deliberative norms? *J. Environ. Policy Plan.* 13, 297–316. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1523908X.2011.607002>.
- Bell, K., Reed, M., 2021. The tree of participation: a new model for inclusive decision-making. *Community Dev. J.* <https://doi.org/10.1093/cdj/bsab018>.
- Blackstock, K.L., Kelly, G.J., Horsey, B.L., 2007. Developing and applying a framework to evaluate participatory research for sustainability. *Ecol. Econ.* 60, 726–742. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2006.05.014>.
- Blair, G., 2015. Survey methods for sensitive topics. *Comp. Polit. Newsl.* 25, 12–15.
- Braunreiter, L., van Beek, L., Hajer, M., van Vuuren, D., 2021. Transformative pathways - using integrated assessment models more effectively to open up plausible and desirable low-carbon futures. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 80. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.102220>.
- Briers, S., Vienni-Baptista, B., 2024. D2.4 Stakeholder-informed research questions. DIAMOND Project. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11236722>.
- Briers, S., Vienni-Baptista, B., 2025. D2.5 - Stakeholder-informed research questions - Update. [Report]. DIAMOND Project.
- Campfens, J.K., Duygan, M., Binder, C.R., 2025. A review of participatory modeling techniques for energy transition scenarios. *Adv. Appl. Energy* 17, 100215. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.AADPEN.2025.100215>.
- Cash, D.W., Clark, W.C., Alcock, F., Dickson, N.M., Eckley, N., Guston, D.H., Jäger, J., Mitchell, R.B., 2003. Knowledge systems for sustainable development. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 100, 8086–8091. <https://doi.org/10.1073/PNAS.1231332100>.
- Castillo-Montoya, M., 2016. Preparing for interview research: the interview protocol refinement framework. *Qual. Rep.* 21, 811–831. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2016.2337>.
- Chu, E., Angelovski, I., Carmin, J.A., 2016. Inclusive approaches to urban climate adaptation planning and implementation in the global south. *Clim. Policy* 16, 372–392. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14693062.2015.1019822>.
- Conklin, J., 2005. Social complexity wicked problems. *Wicked Problems & Social Complexity in Dialogue Mapping: Building Shared Understanding of Wicked Problems*, pp. 1–20.
- Creswell, J.W., Clark, V.L.P., 2017. Designing and conducting mixed methods research. Sage.
- Cvitanić, C., Howden, M., Colvin, R.M., Norström, A., Meadow, A.M., Addison, P.F., 2019. Maximising the benefits of participatory climate adaptation research by understanding and managing the associated challenges and risks. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2018.12.028>.
- Dannecker, P., 2020. Transdisciplinarity 'meets' power structures: challenges and experiences of a capacity building project on transdisciplinarity. *Austrian J. SouthEast Asian Stud.* 13, 175–192. <https://doi.org/10.14764/10.ASEAS-0042>.
- Delafaid, G., Donnison, C., Roddis, P., Arvanitopoulos, T., Sfyridis, A., Dunnett, S., Ball, T., Logan, K.G., 2021. Conceptual framework for balancing society and nature in net-zero energy transitions. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 125, 189–201. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2021.08.021>.
- DIAMOND, 2020. Delivering the next generation of open integrated assessment models for net zero sustainable development. HORIZON-CL5-2022D1-02-03 - Improvement of Integrated Assessment Models in support of climate policies.
- Díaz-Reviriego, I., Turnhout, E., Beck, S., 2019. Participation and inclusiveness in the intergovernmental science-policy platform on biodiversity and ecosystem services. *Nat. Sustain.* 2, 457–464. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0290-6>.
- Doukas, H., Nikas, A., 2020. Decision support models in climate policy. *Eur. J. Oper. Res.* 280, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ejor.2019.01.017>.
- Doukas, H., Nikas, A., González-Eguino, M., Arto, I., Anger-Kraavi, A., 2018. From integrated to integrative: Delivering on the Paris agreement. *Sustainability* 2018, Vol. 10, Page 2299 10, 2299. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su10072299>.
- Ellenbeck, S., Lilliestam, J., 2019. How modelers construct energy costs: Discursive elements in energy system and integrated assessment models. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 47, 69–77. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2018.08.021>.
- Ernst, A., Fischer-Hotzel, A., Schumann, D., 2017. Transforming knowledge for sustainability: Insights from an inclusive science-practice dialogue on low-carbon society in Germany. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 29, 23–35. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2017.04.006>.
- Fazey, I., Schöpke, N., Caniglia, G., Hodgson, A., Kendrick, I., Lyon, C., Page, G., Patterson, J., Riedy, C., Strasser, T., Verveen, S., Adams, D., Goldstein, B., Klaes, M., Leicester, G., Linyard, A., McCurdy, A., Ryan, P., Sharpe, B., Silvestri, G., Abdurrahim, A.Y., Abson, D., Adetunji, O.S., Aldunce, P., Alvarez-Pereira, C., Amparo, J.M., Amundsen, H., Anderson, L., Andersson, L., Asquith, M., Augenstein, K., Barrie, J., Bent, D., Bentz, J., Bergsten, A., Berzonsky, C., Bina, O., Blackstock, K., Boehnert, J., Bradbury, H., Brand, C., Böhme, J., Bøjer, M.M., Carmen, E., Charli-Joseph, L., Choudhury, S., Chunhachoti-ananta, S., Cockburn, J., Colvin, J., Connon, L.L.C., Cornforth, R., Cox, M.S., Cradock-Henry, N., Cramer, L., Cremaschi, A., Dannevig, H., Day, C.T., de Lima Hutchison, C., de Vrieze, A., Desai, V., Dolley, J., Duckett, D., Durrant, R.A., Egermann, M., Elsner, E., Fremantle, C., Fullwood-Thomas, J., Galafassi, D., Gobby, J., Golland, A., González-Padrón, S.K., Gram-Hanssen, I., Grandin, J., Grenni, S., Gunnell, J.L., Gusmao, F., Hamann, M., Harding, B., Harper, G., Hesselgren, M., Hestad, D., Heykoop, C.A., Holmén, J., Holstead, K., Hoolohan, C., Horcea-Milcu, A.-I., Horlings, L.G., Howden, S.M., Howell, R.A., Huque, S.I., Inturias Canedo, M.L., Iro, C.Y., Ives, C.D., John, B., Joshi, R., Juárez-Bourke, S., Juma, D.W., Karlens, B.C., Kliem, L., Kläy, A., Kuenkel, P., Kunze, I., Lam, D.P.M., Lang, D.J., Larkin, A., Light, A., Luederitz, C., Luthe, T., Maguire, C., Mahecha-Groot, A.-M., Malcolm, J., Marshall, F., Maru, Y., McLachlan, C., Mmbando, P., Mohapatra, S., Moore, M.-L., Moriggi, A., Morley-Fletcher, M., Moser, S., Mueller, K.M., Mukute, M., Mühlmeier, S., Naess, L.O., Nieto-Romero, M., Novo, P., O'Brien, K., O'Connell, D.A., O'Donnell, K., Olsson, P., Pearson, K.R., Pereira, L., Petridis, P., Peukert, D., Phear, N., Pisters, S.R., Polsky, M., Pound, D., Preiser, R., Rahman, M.S., Reed, M.S., Revell, P., Rodriguez, I., Rogers, B. C., Rohr, J., Rosenberg, M.N., Ross, H., Russell, S., Ryan, M., Saha, P., Schleicher, K., Schneider, F., Scoville-Simonds, M., Searle, B., Sebhatu, S.P., Sesana, E., Silverman, H., Singh, C., Sterling, E., Stewart, S.-J., Tàbara, J.D., Taylor, D., Thornton, P., Tribaldos, T.M., Tschakert, P., Uribe-Calvo, N., Waddell, S., Waddock, S., van der Merwe, L., van Mierlo, B., van Zwanenberg, P., Velarde, S.J., Washbourne, C.-L., Waylen, K., Weiser, A., Wight, I., Williams, S., Woods, M., Wolstenholme, R., Wright, N., Wunder, S., Wyllie, A., Young, H.R., 2020. Transforming knowledge systems for life on Earth: visions of future systems and how to get there. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 70. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101724>.
- Fraser, N., 2009. Scales of justice: reimagining political space in a globalizing world. Columbia University Press.
- Galende-Sánchez, E., Sorman, A.H., 2021. From consultation toward coproduction in science and policy: A critical systematic review of participatory climate and energy initiatives. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 73. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2020.101907>.
- Gambhir, A., Butnar, I., Li, P.H., Smith, P., Strachan, N., 2019. A review of criticisms of integrated assessment models and proposed approaches to address these, through the lens of beccs. *Energies* 12. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en12091747>.
- Gray, S., Voinov, A., Paolisso, M., Jordan, R., Bendor, T., Bommel, P., Glynn, P., Hedelin, B., Hubacek, K., Introne, J., Kolagani, N., Laursen, B., Prell, C., Olabisi, L.S., Singer, A., Sterling, E., Zellner, M., 2018. Purpose, processes, partnerships, and products: Four ps to advance participatory socio-environmental modeling: four. *Ecol. Appl.* 28, 46–61. <https://doi.org/10.1002/eap.1627>.
- Hedelin, B., Gray, S., Woelke, S., BenDor, T.K., Singer, A., Jordan, R., Zellner, M., Giabbanelli, P., Glynn, P., Jenni, K., Jetter, A., Kolagani, N., Laursen, B., Leong, K.M., Olabisi, L.S., Sterling, E., 2021. What's left before participatory modeling can fully support real-world environmental planning processes: a case study review. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 143. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2021.105073>.
- Jäger, J., Brutschin, E., Pianta, S., Omann, I., Kammerlander, M., Vishwanathan, S.S., Vrontisi, Z., MacDonald, J., van Ruijven, B., 2023. Stakeholder engagement and decarbonization pathways: Meeting the challenges of the COVID-19 pandemic. *Front. Sustain.* <https://doi.org/10.3389/frsus.2022.1063719>.
- Jordan, R., Gray, S., Zellner, M., Glynn, P.D., Voinov, A., Hedelin, B., Sterling, E.J., Leong, K., Olabisi, L.S., Hubacek, K., Bommel, P., BenDor, T.K., Jetter, A.J., Laursen, B., Singer, A., Giabbanelli, P.J., Kolagani, N., Carrera, L.B., Jenni, K., Prell, C., 2018. Twelve questions for the participatory modeling community. *Earth's Future* 6, 1046–1057. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018EF000841>.
- Kallio, H., Pietila, A.M., Johnson, M., Kangasniemi, M., 2016. Systematic methodological review: developing a framework for a qualitative semistructured interview guide. *J. Adv. Nurs.* 72, 2954–2965. <https://doi.org/10.1111/jan.13031>.
- Kawulich, B.B., 2005. Participant observation as a data collection method. *Forum. Qual. Soc. Res.* 6. <https://doi.org/10.17169/fqs-6.2.466>.
- Kenny, D.C., Castilla-Rho, J., 2022. No stakeholder is an island: Human barriers and enablers in participatory environmental modeling. *Land* 11. <https://doi.org/10.3390/land11030340>.
- Keppo, I., Butnar, I., Bauer, N., Caspani, M., Edelenbosch, O., Emmerling, J., Fragkos, P., Guivarch, C., Harmsen, M., Lefevre, J., Gallic, T.L., Leimbach, M., McDowall, W., Mercure, J.F., Schaeffer, R., Trutnevte, E., Wagner, F., 2021. Exploring the possibility space: taking stock of the diverse capabilities and gaps in integrated assessment models. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 16. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1748-9326/abe5d8>.

- Klenk, N., Meehan, K., 2015. Climate change and transdisciplinary science: problematizing the integration imperative. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 54, 160–167. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2015.05.017>.
- Kok, K.P., Gjeffsen, M.D., Regeer, B.J., Broerse, J.E., 2021. Unraveling the politics of 'doing inclusion' in transdisciplinarity for sustainable transformation. *Sustain. Sci.* 16, 1811–1826. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-01033-7>.
- Krawczyk, F., Braun, A.C., 2025. Models like heroes? making integrated assessment models (iams) ready for deep decarbonization and a socioeconomic transformation. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 121, 103959. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2025.103959>.
- Kujala, J., Sachs, S., Leinonen, H., Heikkinen, A., Laude, D., 2022. Stakeholder engagement: past, present, and future. *Bus. Soc.* 61, 1136–1196. <https://doi.org/10.1177/00076503211066595>.
- Kunseler, E.M., Tuinstra, W., Vasileiadou, E., Petersen, A.C., 2015. The reflective futures practitioner: balancing salience, credibility and legitimacy in generating foresight knowledge with stakeholders. *Futures* 66, 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.FUTURES.2014.10.006>.
- Lang, D.J., Wiek, A., Bergmann, M., Stauffacher, M., Martens, P., Moll, P., Swilling, M., Thomas, C.J., 2012. Transdisciplinary research in sustainability science: practice, principles, and challenges. *Sustain. Sci.* 7, 25–43. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-011-0149-x>.
- Lemos, M.C., Arnott, J.C., Ardoin, N.M., Baja, K., Bednarek, A.T., Dewulf, A., Fieseler, C., Goodrich, K.A., Jagannathan, K., Klenk, N., Mach, K.J., Meadow, A.M., Meyer, R., Moss, R., Nichols, L., Sjöstrom, K.D., Stults, M., Turnhout, E., Vaughan, C., Wong-Parodi, G., Wyborn, C., 2018. To co-produce or not to co-produce. *Nat. Sustain.* 722–724. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-018-0191-0>.
- Lenzner, T., Menold, N., 2016. Gesis survey guidelines question wording [doi:10.15465/gesis-sg-en.017](https://doi.org/10.15465/gesis-sg-en.017).
- Lieu, J., Martínez-Reyes, A., Groome, P., Mangalagu, D., Pearce, B.B.J., Witajewska-Baltvilka, B., Möller, R.E.D., 2023. Inclusive stakeholder engagement for equitable knowledge co-production insights from the eu's horizon 2020 programme in climate change research. *GAIA Ecol. Perspect. Sci. Soc.* 32, 138–143. <https://doi.org/10.14512/gaia.32.1.11>.
- Lim, T.C., Glynn, P.D., Shenk, G.W., Bitterman, P., Guillaume, J.H.A., Little, J.C., Webster, D.G., 2023. Recognizing political influences in participatory social-ecological systems modeling. *SocioEnviron. Syst. Model.* 5, 18509. <https://doi.org/10.18174/sesmo.18509>.
- Linneberg, M.S., Korsgaard, S., 2019. Coding qualitative data: a synthesis guiding the novice. *Qual. Res. J.* 19, 259–270. <https://doi.org/10.1108/QRJ-12-2018-0012>.
- Lochmiller, C.R., 2021. Conducting thematic analysis with qualitative data. *Qual. Rep.* 26, 2029–2044. <https://doi.org/10.46743/2160-3715/2021.5008>.
- Low, S., Schäfer, S., 2020. Is bio-energy carbon capture and storage (beccs) feasible? the contested authority of integrated assessment modeling. *Energy Research Social Science* 60, 101326. [doi:10.1016/J.ERSS.2019.101326](https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2019.101326).
- Mader, M., Pohl, C., 2024. Aligning processes and outcomes with external stakeholders: CASE 4: TRANSDISCIPLINARY COURSES WITH STAKEHOLDERS COPRODUCING KNOWLEDGE. Taylor and Francis. pp. 98–100. [doi:10.4324/9781003286004-6](https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003286004-6).
- Mausser, W., Klepper, G., Rice, M., Schmalzbauer, B.S., Hackmann, H., Leemans, R., Moore, H., 2013. Transdisciplinary global change research: the co-creation of knowledge for sustainability. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 5, 420–431. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.COSUST.2013.07.001>.
- McGookin, C., Gallachoir, B.O., Byrne, E., 2021. Participatory methods in energy system modeling and planning - a review. *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.* 151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rser.2021.111504>.
- McGookin, C., Süsler, D., Xexakis, G., Trutnevte, E., McDowall, W., Nikas, A., Koasidis, K., Few, S., Andersen, P.D., Demski, C., Fortes, P., Simoes, S.G., Bishop, C., Rogan, F., Gallachoir, B., 2024. Advancing participatory energy systems modeling. *Energy Strategy Rev.* 52. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.esr.2024.101319>.
- McGookin, C., Uidhir, T.M., Gallachoir, B., Byrne, E., 2022. Doing things differently: bridging community concerns and energy system modeling with a transdisciplinary approach in rural Ireland. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 89, 102658. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2022.102658>.
- McLaren, D., Markusson, N., 2020. The co-evolution of technological promises, modeling, policies and climate change targets. *Nat. Clim. Change* 10, 392–397. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-0740-1>.
- Meadow, A.M., Ferguson, D.B., Guido, Z., Horangic, A., Owen, G., Wall, T., 2015. Moving toward the deliberate coproduction of climate science knowledge. *Weather Clim. Soc.* 7, 179–191. <https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-14-00050.1>.
- Milanzi, N., Schelly, C., 2025. Meaningful engagement in transitions research: care and value in research partnerships. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 170, 104120. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104120>.
- Miller, C.A., Wyborn, C., 2020. Co-production in global sustainability: histories and theories. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 113, 88–95. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVSCI.2018.01.016>.
- Montfort, S., Fesenfeld, L., Ingold, K., Lamb, W.F., Andrijevic, M., 2025. Political enablers of ambitious climate policies: a framework and thematic review. *npj Clim. Action* 4, 14. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s44168-024-00206-1>.
- Nikas, A., Lieu, J., Sorman, A., Gambhir, A., Turhan, E., Baptista, B.V., Doukas, H., 2020. The desirability of transitions in demand: Incorporating behavioural and societal transformations into energy modeling. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 70, 101780. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2020.101780>.
- Nikas, A., Xexakis, G., Koasidis, K., Acosta-Fernández, J., Arto, I., Calzadilla, A., Domenech, T., Gambhir, A., Giljum, S., Gonzalez-Eguino, M., Herbst, A., Ivanova, O., van Sluisveld, M., Ven, D.J.V.D., Karamaneas, A., Doukas, H., 2022. Coupling circularity performance and climate action: From disciplinary silos to transdisciplinary modeling science. *Sustain. Prod. Consum.* 30, 269–277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.spc.2021.12.011>.
- Nogueira, L.A., Björkan, M., Dale, B., 2021. Conducting research in a postnormal paradigm: Practical guidance for applying co-production of knowledge. *Front. Environ. Sci.* 9. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fenvs.2021.699397>.
- Norström, A.V., Cvitanovic, C., Lof, M.F., West, S., Wyborn, C., Balvanera, P., Bednarek, A.T., Bennett, E.M., Biggs, R., de Bremond, A., Campbell, B.M., Canadell, J.G., Carpenter, S.R., Folke, C., Fulton, E.A., Gaffney, O., Gelcich, S., Jouffray, J.B., Leach, M., Tissier, M.L., Martín-López, B., Louder, E., Loutre, M.F., Meadow, A.M., Nagendra, H., Payne, D., Peterson, G.D., Reyers, B., Scholes, R., Speranza, C.I., Spierenburg, M., Stafford-Smith, M., Tengö, M., van der Hel, S., van Putten, I., Osterblom, H., 2020. Principles for knowledge coproduction in sustainability research. *Nat. Sustain.* 3, 182–190. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41893-019-0448-2>.
- Parzonko, H., Sonnino, R., Timotijevic, L., 2025. Procedural justice in participatory food system governance: an integrated framework. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 174, 104269. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104269>.
- Peng, W., Bosetti, V., Chaturvedi, V., Edmonds, J., Fawcett, A.A., Hallegatte, S., Victor, D.G., van Vuuren, D., Weyant, J., 2021. Climate policy models need to get real about people-here's how. *Nat. Comment.* <https://doi.org/10.1038/d41586-021-01500-2>.
- Pisano, U., Lange, L.K., Lepuschitz, K., Berger, G., 2015. The role of stakeholder participation in European sustainable development policies and strategies. *eSDN Quarterly Report No 39*.
- Pohl, C., Klein, J.T., Hoffmann, S., Mitchell, C., Fam, D., 2021. Conceptualising transdisciplinary integration as a multidimensional interactive process. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 118, 18–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2020.12.005>.
- Priest, H., Roberts, P., Woods, L., 2002. An overview of three different approaches to the interpretation of qualitative data. part 1: theoretical issues. *Nurse Res.* 10, 30–42. <https://doi.org/10.7748/nr2002.10.10.1.30.c5877>.
- Punjabi, S., Misra, S., Rippl, M.A., Grant, S.B., Galappaththi, E., Lim, T., Birkland, T.A., 2025. A conceptual framework for knowledge integration in cross-disciplinary collaborations. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 172, 104197. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104197>.
- Ravikumar, A.P., Baker, E., Bates, A., Nock, D., Venkataraman, D., Johnson, T., Ash, M., Attari, S.Z., Bowie, K., Carley, S., Castellanos, S., Cha, M., Clark, D.L., Deane-Ryan, D., Djokic, D., Ford, J.C., Goldstein, A., Grubert, E., Hu, L., Kammen, D.M., Kosar, U., Miller, C., Pastor, M., Tuominen, M., 2022. Enabling an equitable energy transition through inclusive research. *Nat. Energy* 1–4. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-022-01145-z>.
- Roelfsema, M., van Soest, H.L., den Elzen, M., de Coninck, H., Kuramochi, T., Harmsen, M., Dafnomilis, I., Hohne, N., van Vuuren, D.P., 2022. Developing scenarios in the context of the Paris agreement and application in the integrated assessment model image: A framework for bridging the policy-modeling divide. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 135, 104–116. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2022.05.001>.
- Royston, S., Foulds, C., Pasqualino, R., Jones, A., 2023. Masters of the machinery: The politics of economic modeling within European union energy policy. *Energy Policy* 173. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enpol.2022.113386>.
- Rubiano Rivadeneira, N., Carton, W., 2022. (In)justice in modelled climate futures: A review of integrated assessment modelling critiques through a justice lens. *Energy Research & Social Science* 92, 102781. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ERSS.2022.102781>.
- Schmidt, L., Falk, T., Siegmund-Schultze, M., Spangenberg, J.H., 2020. The objectives of stakeholder involvement in transdisciplinary research: a conceptual framework for a reflective and reflexive practice. *Ecol. Econ.* 176. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ecolecon.2020.106751>.
- Schoonover, H.A., Grêt-Regamey, A., Metzger, M.J., Ruiz-Frau, A., Santos-Reis, M., Scholte, S.S.K., Walz, A., Nicholas, K.A., 2019. Creating space, aligning motivations, and building trust: a practical framework for stakeholder engagement based on experience in 12 ecosystem services case studies. *Ecol. Soc. Publ. Online.* <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-10061-240111>.
- Selloni, D., Research for Development CoDesign for Public-Interest Services. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-53243-1>.
- Sorgen, J., Nelson, P., Butsic, V., LaRosa, S., Gaughen, S., Crosby, E., Geary, R., Sowerwine, J., 2025. Unchecking the box: overcoming barriers to meaningful consultation. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 169, 104085. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104085>.
- Steen, T., Brandsen, T., Verschuere, B., 2018. The dark side of co-creation and co-production: Seven evils. *Co-Production and Co-Creation*, pp. 284–293. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315204956-45>.
- Sterling, E.J., Zellner, M., Jenni, K.E., Leong, K., Glynn, P.D., BenDor, T.K., Bommel, P., Hubacek, K., Jetter, A.J., Jordan, R., Olabisi, L.S., Paolisso, M., Gray, S., 2019. Try, try again: Lessons learned from success and failure in participatory modeling. *Elementa* 7. <https://doi.org/10.1525/elementa.347>.
- Stirling, A., 2006. Analysis, participation and power: Justification and closure in participatory multi-criteria analysis. *Land Use Policy* 23, 95–107. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.landusepol.2004.08.010>.
- Süsser, D., Ceglaz, A., Gaschnig, H., Stavrakas, V., Flamos, A., Giannakidis, G., Lilliestam, J., 2021. Model-based policymaking or policybased modeling? how energy models and energy policy interact. *Energy Res. Soc. Sci.* 75. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.erss.2021.101984>.
- Toepfel, V., 2016. Doing Surveys Online. SAGE Publications Ltd. <https://doi.org/10.4135/9781473967243>.
- Turnhout, E., Metzger, T., Wyborn, C., Klenk, N., Louder, E., 2020. The politics of co-production: participation, power, and transformation. *Curr. Opin. Environ. Sustain.* 42, 15–21. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cosust.2019.11.009>.
- UN, 2024. The sustainable development goals report 2024. ISBN: 9789213589762.

- UNEP, 2024. Emissions gap report 2024: No more hot air... please! [doi:10.59117/20.500.11822/46404](https://doi.org/10.59117/20.500.11822/46404).
- UNFCCC, 2024. [Nationally determined contributions under the paris agreement](https://www.unfccc.int/nationally-determined-contributions).
- van Beek, L., Hajer, M., Pelzer, P., van Vuuren, D., Cassen, C., 2020. Anticipating futures through models: the rise of integrated assessment modeling in the climate science-policy interface since 1970. *Glob. Environ. Change* 65, 102191. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.GLOENVCHA.2020.102191>.
- van Beek, L., Oomen, J., Hajer, M., Pelzer, P., van Vuuren, D., 2022. Navigating the political: An analysis of political calibration of integrated assessment modeling in light of the 1.5°C goal. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 133, 193–202. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVSCI.2022.03.024>.
- Voinov, A., Jenni, K., Gray, S., Kolagani, N., Glynn, P.D., Bommel, P., Prell, C., Zellner, M., Paolisso, M., Jordan, R., Sterling, E., Olabisi, L.S., Giabbanelli, P.J., Sun, Z., Page, C.L., Elsayah, S., BenDor, T.K., Hubacek, K., Laursen, B.K., Jetter, A., Basco-Carrera, L., Singer, A., Young, L., Brunacini, J., Smajgl, A., 2018. Tools and methods in participatory modeling: selecting the right tool for the job. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 109, 232–255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVSOFT.2018.08.028>.
- Voinov, A., Kolagani, N., McCall, M.K., Glynn, P.D., Kragt, M.E., Ostermann, F.O., Pierce, S.A., Ramu, P., 2016. Modeling with stakeholders - next generation. *Environ. Model. Softw.* 77, 196–220. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsoft.2015.11.016>.
- Wesselink, A., Paavola, J., Fritsch, O., Renn, O., 2011. Rationales for public participation in environmental policy and governance: practitioners' perspectives. *Environ. Plan. A Econ. Space* 43, 2688–2704. <https://doi.org/10.1068/A44161>.
- Weyant, J., 2017. Some contributions of integrated assessment models of global climate change. *Rev. Environ. Econ. Policy* 11, 115–137. <https://doi.org/10.1093/reep/rew018>.
- Wilson, A.M., Polk, E., Field, C.B., Fendorf, S., 2025. Towards environmental justice: a framework and strategic approach for implementing community based participatory research in the earth and environmental sciences. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 167, 104036. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envsci.2025.104036>.
- Workman, M., Dooley, K., Lomax, G., Maltby, J., Darch, G., 2020. Decision making in contexts of deep uncertainty - an alternative approach for longterm climate policy. *Environ. Sci. Policy* 103, 77–84. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.ENVSCI.2019.10.002>.
- Xiao, Y., Watson, M., 2019. Guidance on conducting a systematic literature review. *J. Plan. Educ. Res.* 39, 93–112. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0739456X17723971>.
- Zurba, M., Petriello, M.A., Madge, C., McCarney, P., Bishop, B., McBeth, S., Denniston, M., Bodwitch, H., Bailey, M., 2022. Learning from knowledge co-production research and practice in the twenty-first century: global lessons and what they mean for collaborative research in nunatsiavut. *Sustain. Sci.* 17, 449–467. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11625-021-00996-x>.